

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Feasibility study into ice sheet-ocean model initialisation

Deliverable D3.4

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Cover sheet: Estimating parameters of the WAVI ice sheet model using Ensemble Kalman Inversion.

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	1 October 2025	Submitted version	Robert Arthern
Version 2	3 March 2026	Correction of the caption in Figure 5	Robert Arthern

1. Publishable summary

This deliverable describes a feasibility study into using Ensemble Kalman Inversion to initialise coupled Ice-Ocean Models. A manuscript describing the technical details of the research has been submitted to The Cryosphere (Bradley et al. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-2315>). This report provides a brief introduction to the methods used and illustrative results from the submitted manuscript. Additionally, we provide links to public code repositories where examples of the methods are implemented, along with relevant code snippets. In performing this feasibility study, we have made four key findings:

- Ensemble Kalman Inversion (EKI) can be successfully used to constrain parameters in ice-sheet models with simplified ocean-driven melting schemes, making the approach feasible.
- EKI can be deployed effectively as part of a Calibrate-Emulate-Sample (CES) strategy.
- Combining EKI and CES allows probabilistic assessment of parameters.
- This, in turn, will allow uncertainty quantification, probabilistic attribution studies, and forecasts of the risk posed by marine ice sheets.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Applying the Ensemble Kalman Filter with WAVI

Model State: Coupled Ice/Ocean models evolve a collection of variables to represent the changes of the ice sheet and the surrounding ocean. Together, these variables (ice thickness, ocean velocity, pressure, temperature, salinity, etc.) represent the model state.

KF: The Kalman Filter (KF) provides an efficient means for updating a model state so that it agrees with observations. The algorithm also provides a corresponding update to the error covariance. After a succession of sequential observations, good estimates of the state variables and their errors can be obtained.

EnKF: Retaining the full error covariance matrix in the calculations can be expensive. This led to the development of the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF; Evenson, 1994). Here, a collection of model runs (i.e. an ensemble) is performed, and the sample covariance of this ensemble is used in place of the full covariance matrix.

IEnKF/IEnKS: Non-linear models require an additional iteration loop, the Iterative Ensemble Kalman Filter (IEnKF). If the observational data are included altogether, rather than sequentially, the method is referred to as an Iterative Ensemble Kalman Smoother (IEnKS; Bocquet and Sakov, 2013).

Model Parameters: As well as state variables, coupled ice/ocean models also contain physical parameters (viscosity, drag coefficients, etc.). If these are not specified accurately, the model will provide inaccurate projections of sea level.

EKI: When Ensemble Kalman methods are used, but the focus is on estimating the best values for parameters, rather than state variables, this is sometimes referred to as Ensemble Kalman Inversion.

Implementation.

To deploy the methods above, we have combined:

- 1) **EnsembleKalmanProcesses.jl**: A Julia package implementing the Ensemble Kalman Filter.
- 2) **model-ensampler**: A tool for managing processes on a SLURM cluster.
- 3) **WAVI.jl**: An ice sheet model written in Julia.

Fig. 1: Estimating parameters of the WAVI ice sheet model using Ensemble Kalman Inversion.

2.1.2 Applying the Calibrate Emulate Sample methodology with WAVI

Using Ensemble Kalman Inversion on its own will provide an updated set of parameter values that are better constrained by the observations. Usually, the size of the ensemble is relatively small, so the sample of parameter values within the ensemble cannot provide a complete representation of the probability that parameters will take any particular value. Furthermore, because EKI assumes that the probability density function can be represented by its mean and covariance statistics, there is no guarantee that the members of the ensemble are distributed according to the actual probability distribution. The latter concern becomes especially important if the posterior probability density of the parameter values deviates from a Gaussian, for example, skewed distributions with asymmetric tails.

The concerns of poor sampling and non-Gaussian PDFs become particularly acute for our application of sea level projection. This is because a key piece of information required by policymakers relates to high-impact-low-likelihood scenarios of high sea level rise that lie far in the tails of the probability density function. Such low-probability events are unlikely to be represented within the few samples contained in the EKI ensemble. Representing the upper tail of the highly skewed sea level PDF also demands that we address the possibility of a non-Gaussian probability density. Fortunately, both concerns can be addressed using a new machine-learning methodology referred to as Calibrate-Emulate-Sample (CES; Cleary et al. 2021).

In collaboration with the PROTECT project, we have extended our original plan to use EKI. We now embed the EKI procedure as just one step in the more complete CES framework.

CES proceeds in three stages.

The **Calibrate** stage utilizes EKI to update an initial parameter ensemble using observations, ensuring that the parameters within the ensemble lie in a part of parameter space that better aligns with the observations.

The **Emulate** stage uses the calibrated ensemble to train an emulator of the ice sheet model. This emulator is designed to efficiently predict the model output that would be obtained for any proposed parameter values. Because a calibrated ensemble that densely samples the most likely part of parameter space is used to train the emulator, we expect the emulator to perform particularly well in this high-likelihood region.

The **Sample** stage uses the Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo method to make repeated samples from the posterior PDF. Rather than use the full ice sheet model, this stage uses the efficient emulator.

Fig. 2: The **Calibrate-Emulate-Sample (CES)** approach. **Calibrate:** using Ensemble Kalman Inversion moves initial guesses for parameters closer to the region of high probability (shaded dark). **Emulate:** using Gaussian Processes allows an approximate model of the simulator to be derived from the calibrated ensemble of parameters. This enables rapid evaluation of an approximation to the likelihood function without running the expensive model. **Sample:** the emulator is used with a Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo (MCMC) algorithm to draw samples from the posterior more densely than the original ensemble and in a way that more faithfully represents the underlying probabilities.

2.2 References

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Bradley, A. T., Bett, D. T., Williams, C. R., Arthern, R. J., Holland, P. R., Bryne, J., and Edwards, T. L.: Quantifying and attributing the role of anthropogenic climate change in industrial-era retreat of Pine Island Glacier, *EGU sphere* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-2315>, 2025.

Cleary, E., Garbuno-Inigo, A., Lan, S., Schneider, T., Stuart, A.M., 2021: Calibrate, emulate, sample, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 424, 109716. doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2020.109716

2.3 Open Science

Code: The code to implement EKI using the WAVI Ice sheet model and model-ensampler is available at https://github.com/WAVI-ice-sheet-model/EKI_idealised_PIG-example. This code is also archived at <https://zenodo.org/records/17224508>.

The code to implement the examples from Bradley et al. (submitted) is available at <https://github.com/alexbradley/PIG-CES> and archived at <https://zenodo.org/records/17209677>.

Peer-reviewed publications:

A publication in open access has been submitted to The Cryosphere <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-2315>

Cite as: Bradley, A. T., Bett, D. T., Williams, C. R., Arthern, R. J., Holland, P. R., Bryne, J., and Edwards, T. L.: Quantifying and attributing the role of anthropogenic climate change in industrial-era retreat of Pine Island Glacier, EGU sphere [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-2315>, 2025. The authors have selected a CC BY licence. There is no embargo period.

3. Results

The main result is proof of the feasibility of using Ensemble Kalman Inversion to initialise coupled ice-ocean models. Selected results are illustrated below. See Bradley et al. (submitted) for complete details.

Fig. 3: Calibration of model parameters for the WAVI ice sheet model using Ensemble Kalman Inversion (EKI). In all panels, results are shown progressing from 1 (dark blue) to 5 (light blue) iterations of EKI. As the iterations progress, the model results come closer to the observations of grounded volume (a) and grounding line retreat (b). The observations are plotted in red. The spread of model parameters (c-h) reduces as the number of iterations increases. For full details, see Bradley et al (submitted).

Fig. 4: An example of emulating the output of the WAVI ice sheet model using Gaussian Processes. The figure shows results produced using the full ice sheet model plotted against results produced by the emulator. The emulator is much cheaper to run than the full model, which opens the possibility of using Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo methods to characterise the PDF of model parameters. For full details, see Bradley et al. (submitted).

Fig. 5: Illustrative examples of prior (dark blue) and posterior (light blue) probability density function (PDF) for parameters in the WAVI ice sheet model. For each parameter, the narrow lines indicate the 95% interval, thick lines indicate the interquartile range, and black points indicate the median. Individual posterior PDFs are also shown for 14 individual realisations of climate forcing. For full details, see Bradley et al. (submitted).

Our results have also contributed to the following areas:

- **Know-how and innovative solutions:** New applications of EKI and CES to ice sheet model initialisation. This has opened up a new avenue for performing attribution experiments on marine ice sheets (Bradley et al., Submitted).
- **Algorithms, prototypes, and demonstrators:** Worked examples published in publicly available repositories.
- **Trained researchers:** Postdoctoral researchers familiar with EKI and CES in glaciology/oceanography.
- **New infrastructure:** Digital infrastructure published online in a format suitable for use by Digital Twins.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following project objectives as described in the description of the action.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-climate models.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing techniques to initialise ice sheet models in a probabilistic framework that allows uncertainty to be quantified.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing techniques to initialise ice sheet models, allowing accurate forecasts of the ice sheets and their freshwater delivery to the ocean.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing techniques to initialise ice sheet models, allowing accurate hindcasts of the ice sheets and their freshwater delivery to the ocean.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g., IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g., SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance), and policymakers.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing illustrative examples of how to apply Ensemble Kalman Inversion for ice sheet modelling on publicly available code repositories.